

Designing a Deep Learning Model for Snake Identification in Sri Lanka: A Literature-Guided Approach

Udayanga S.A.C.^{1*}, Dissanayaka W.V.S.², Herath H.M.D.S.³

¹*Faculty of Information Technology, Horizon Campus, Malabe, Sri Lanka.*

Abstract

In Sri Lanka, snake envenoming remains a major health and ecological challenge. Even though Sri Lanka is home to more than 108 snake species, snake identification constitutes a critical gap, which leads to inefficient treatments and snake conservation efforts. Currently, 35% of snakebite cases go unidentified, while snake-human conflict has further escalated due to myths and misidentification. Regardless of the progress of computer vision and species identification on a global scale, the existing datasets suffer from issues such as class imbalance and regional bias, which make them virtually useless during emergencies in the context of Sri Lanka. To analyze, interpret, and synthesize existing literature, a thematic literature review was conducted by utilizing the aid of academic databases such as IEEE Xplore and Lens.org, targeting existing datasets, deep learning architectures, evaluation strategies, and real-world applications of snake identification systems. This review indicates that Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), especially lightweight models such as MobileNet and EfficientNet, offer adequate performance in resource-constrained environments, while Vision Transformers (ViTs) demonstrate higher accuracy on large-scale data, yet remain computationally demanding. The hybrid and ensemble approaches bring forth promising results by incorporating the higher efficiency of lightweight models and the superior accuracy of ViTs. The review also highlights that dataset quality, including class balance, labeling accuracy, and background realism, directly impacts model performance and its ability to generalize. Essentially, this review demonstrates the need for localized, well-annotated, and balanced datasets, which can be utilized to train lightweight CNN models by integrating hybrid strategies with ViTs for improved accuracy. This will ultimately result in mobile and web-based applications that will enhance medical decision-making, support biodiversity conservation, and reduce unnecessary snake killings in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: *Snake Species Classification, Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Vision Transformers (ViTs), Sri Lanka.*